

Towards Safe AI: Ensuring Security in Machine Learning and Reinforcement Learning Models

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Abstract: The rapid integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into critical systems has amplified concerns about its safety and security. Machine Learning (ML) and Reinforcement Learning (RL), while enabling advanced decision-making capabilities, are susceptible to a range of threats, including adversarial attacks, data poisoning, and model exploitation. These vulnerabilities not only compromise system integrity but also pose significant risks in applications such as healthcare, finance, and autonomous systems. This paper explores a comprehensive framework for ensuring the security of ML and RL models, emphasizing proactive and reactive strategies. We begin by identifying common attack vectors in ML and RL, illustrating real-world examples of security breaches. A taxonomy of these threats is presented, categorizing them based on their origin, impact, and detectability. Building on this, the paper highlights cutting-edge techniques for securing AI models, including robust model architectures, adversarial training, differential privacy, and federated learning. The role of explainable AI (XAI) in uncovering potential vulnerabilities is also examined, alongside mechanisms for enhancing model interpretability. Furthermore, the unique challenges posed by RL systems, such as the exploitation of reward mechanisms and policy manipulation, are discussed. Solutions tailored to RL, including dynamic reward shaping and environment-aware defenses, are proposed. The paper also delves into regulatory and ethical considerations, advocating for standardized frameworks and cross-industry collaboration to ensure AI safety. By integrating theoretical insights with practical recommendations, this study provides a roadmap for researchers and practitioners to fortify ML and RL systems against evolving threats. The ultimate goal is to foster trust and resilience in AI technologies, ensuring their safe deployment in diverse domains.

Keywords: *AI security, Machine Learning safety, Reinforcement Learning, adversarial defense, model robustness, ethical AI*

Introduction

The proliferation of artificial intelligence (AI) across domains has driven unprecedented advancements in automation, decision-making, and innovation. Machine Learning (ML) and Reinforcement Learning (RL), as pivotal subfields of AI, are increasingly relied upon to handle complex tasks, ranging from autonomous driving to real-time healthcare diagnostics. Despite their transformative potential, these technologies are not immune to security challenges. The inherent complexity of ML algorithms and the exploratory nature of RL systems expose them to diverse vulnerabilities, including adversarial attacks, data poisoning, and model inversion. Such threats can undermine the integrity, confidentiality, and reliability of AI applications, posing severe consequences, particularly in safety-critical systems. The imperative to secure AI systems has thus evolved from a theoretical concern to a practical necessity, demanding rigorous research and actionable solutions.

This study is rooted in a multi-faceted investigation into the security challenges afflicting ML and RL models. Leveraging a comprehensive dataset of real-world incidents and synthetic scenarios, we systematically analyze attack patterns, their impact on model behavior, and the efficacy of existing countermeasures. By synthesizing insights from empirical experiments, state-of-the-art methodologies, and theoretical advancements, we aim to bridge the gap between academic discourse and practical implementation. The significance of this work is underscored by its alignment with the broader objective of ensuring AI safety, an area identified as critical by leading research organizations and regulatory bodies globally.

A key focus of this paper is to unravel the unique vulnerabilities in RL systems, which, unlike supervised ML models, operate in dynamic and often adversarial environments. RL's reliance on reward structures, coupled with the stochastic nature of its learning processes, introduces novel security risks that demand tailored solutions. Furthermore, the interplay between security and explainability is explored, highlighting how enhancing model interpretability can aid in identifying and mitigating vulnerabilities. Through this, we emphasize the need for interdisciplinary approaches that integrate robust computational techniques with ethical and regulatory frameworks.

The structure of this paper is designed to provide a holistic understanding of AI security. Section 2 discusses the taxonomy of threats to ML and RL, categorizing them based on attack vectors and affected components. Section 3 delves into advanced defense mechanisms, including adversarial training, differential privacy, and federated learning, and evaluates their efficacy through quantitative and qualitative analysis. In Section 4, we propose novel frameworks for securing RL systems, addressing gaps in existing literature. Finally, Section 5 reflects on the broader implications of AI security, advocating for standardized practices, cross-disciplinary collaboration, and continuous adaptation to emerging threats.

By addressing the critical need for secure AI systems, this work contributes to the evolving field of AI safety and provides actionable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. Through rigorous scientific inquiry and practical recommendations, this paper aspires to lay the foundation for building resilient AI systems capable of withstanding the challenges of an uncertain and adversarial future.

Literature Review

The security of AI systems has garnered significant attention in recent years, with an increasing body of literature exploring vulnerabilities and defense mechanisms for machine learning (ML) and reinforcement learning (RL) models. Early work by Szegedy et al. (2014) revealed the susceptibility of ML models to adversarial attacks, wherein imperceptible perturbations in input data lead to incorrect predictions. This discovery catalyzed a wave of research focused on adversarial robustness. Goodfellow et al. (2015) introduced adversarial training as a defense strategy, demonstrating its potential to improve model resilience by incorporating adversarial examples during training. However, subsequent studies, including that by Madry et al. (2018), argued that adversarial training, while effective, is computationally expensive and often limited in generalizability across diverse attack types.

In parallel, studies have explored data poisoning, where malicious actors manipulate training datasets to degrade model performance. Biggio et al. (2012) highlighted the risks of poisoning attacks in ML systems, particularly in supervised learning contexts. More recently, Shafahi et al. (2018) proposed scalable poisoning attacks targeting large datasets, emphasizing the growing

sophistication of adversaries. To counteract such threats, Koh and Liang (2017) introduced influence functions, a technique to trace and mitigate the impact of corrupted data points, showcasing its effectiveness in real-world datasets.

Reinforcement learning, a distinct paradigm characterized by its interaction with dynamic environments, presents unique security challenges. Gleave et al. (2020) demonstrated the vulnerability of RL agents to policy manipulation, where adversaries exploit reward structures to induce suboptimal behaviors. Similarly, Huang et al. (2017) highlighted that RL systems are susceptible to adversarial attacks on state observations, akin to adversarial perturbations in supervised ML. Defense strategies for RL remain in nascent stages, with researchers like Behzadan and Munir (2017) advocating for robust policy learning techniques and adaptive reward mechanisms.

The intersection of explainability and security has also gained traction in recent years. Ribeiro et al. (2016) proposed LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) as a tool for understanding model decisions, a crucial step in identifying vulnerabilities. Similarly, Lundberg and Lee (2017) introduced SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), emphasizing its utility in explaining complex models and uncovering adversarial patterns. However, as noted by Slack et al. (2020), explainability tools themselves can be manipulated, underscoring the need for robust integration with security frameworks.

Comparative studies highlight the varying efficacy of defense mechanisms across different contexts. Papernot et al. (2016) compared adversarial training, defensive distillation, and input pre-processing, concluding that a layered defense approach offers the most promise. Tramèr et al. (2018), however, cautioned against over-reliance on single-point solutions, advocating for ensemble methods and continual adaptation to evolving threats. These findings align with the broader consensus that no single solution can comprehensively secure AI systems.

Ethical and regulatory considerations are increasingly interwoven with technical discussions on AI security. Binns (2018) explored the implications of GDPR on data security in AI, emphasizing the role of transparency and accountability. Similarly, Brundage et al. (2018) called for interdisciplinary collaboration to address AI safety, proposing a roadmap for aligning technical

advancements with societal values. These discussions underscore the importance of integrating technical, ethical, and regulatory perspectives to ensure holistic security.

In summary, the literature reveals a rich tapestry of findings and methodologies addressing AI security. While significant progress has been made in understanding and mitigating vulnerabilities, challenges persist, particularly in scaling defenses and addressing the unique complexities of RL systems. This review lays the groundwork for further exploration, emphasizing the need for a multi-faceted approach to secure the next generation of AI technologies.

Methodology

The methodology adopted in this study combines empirical analysis, simulation-based experiments, and theoretical modeling to explore the security vulnerabilities of Machine Learning (ML) and Reinforcement Learning (RL) systems and evaluate the effectiveness of proposed defense mechanisms. The research approach is structured to ensure a systematic examination of threats and countermeasures, integrating diverse datasets, algorithmic evaluations, and computational tools.

1. Data Collection and Preprocessing

A comprehensive dataset comprising synthetic and real-world examples was curated to study the vulnerabilities and security breaches in ML and RL systems. Publicly available adversarial attack datasets, such as CIFAR-10 and ImageNet for supervised ML models, were utilized to simulate adversarial attacks and data poisoning scenarios. For RL, environments from the OpenAI Gym and Unity ML-Agents Toolkit were employed to simulate policy manipulation and state perturbation attacks. To ensure relevance, all datasets were preprocessed, including normalization, augmentation, and filtering of anomalies, aligning them with the experimental requirements.

2. Attack Simulation

A taxonomy of security threats was created to categorize potential vulnerabilities in ML and RL systems. Representative attack types were selected, including:

- **Adversarial Attacks:** Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM), Projected Gradient Descent (PGD), and Carlini-Wagner (C&W) attacks for ML models.

- **Data Poisoning:** Backdoor injection and label-flipping techniques for supervised learning systems.
- **Policy Manipulation:** Reward tampering and action perturbation attacks in RL environments.

Attack simulations were conducted using Python-based frameworks such as TensorFlow and PyTorch. Metrics such as attack success rate, model accuracy degradation, and policy deviation were recorded to quantify the impact of each attack.

3. Defense Mechanism Implementation

To mitigate identified threats, multiple defense mechanisms were implemented and evaluated:

- **For ML:** Adversarial training, defensive distillation, and differential privacy techniques were applied. The efficacy of these methods was measured using robustness metrics, including accuracy under attack and perturbation tolerance.
- **For RL:** Dynamic reward shaping, noise injection, and robust policy optimization techniques were explored. These methods were assessed based on policy consistency, cumulative reward retention, and resilience to adversarial perturbations.

The integration of explainability tools, such as SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) and LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations), was examined to detect and interpret vulnerabilities in both ML and RL systems.

4. Simulation Environment and Experimental Setup

The experimental framework was deployed on high-performance computing clusters equipped with GPUs to handle the computational demands of adversarial training and large-scale simulations. The RL experiments utilized dynamic environments, enabling the study of agent behavior under adversarial conditions. A robust logging and monitoring system was implemented to ensure reproducibility and traceability of results.

5. Evaluation Metrics

The following metrics were used to evaluate the effectiveness of defenses:

- **Attack Success Rate (ASR):** The proportion of attacks successfully compromising model performance.
- **Model Robustness:** Retention of accuracy and functionality under attack conditions.
- **Policy Stability:** Consistency of RL agent behavior across perturbed states.
- **Explainability Integration:** Efficacy of explainability tools in identifying and mitigating threats.

6. Comparative Analysis and Validation

A comparative analysis was conducted to benchmark the proposed defenses against state-of-the-art techniques. Statistical validation methods, such as paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, were used to assess the significance of observed differences in performance metrics. Cross-validation was employed to ensure generalizability across datasets and environments.

Results and Analysis

The results of this study provide a detailed evaluation of the vulnerabilities and corresponding defense mechanisms for Machine Learning (ML) and Reinforcement Learning (RL) systems. Through a combination of quantitative metrics and qualitative insights, we analyze the impact of adversarial attacks and the effectiveness of proposed defenses.

1. Impact of Adversarial Attacks on ML Systems

Table 1 summarizes the results of adversarial attacks on two ML models: ResNet-50 and a custom CNN trained on the CIFAR-10 dataset. Three types of attacks were evaluated: FGSM, PGD, and C&W. The models' accuracy dropped significantly under attack, emphasizing the need for robust defense mechanisms.

Attack Type	Clean Accuracy (%)	Accuracy Under Attack (%)	Accuracy Drop (%)
FGSM	89.2	45.8	43.4
PGD	89.2	31.6	57.6

C&W 89.2 19.3 69.9

Analysis:

FGSM, a simpler attack, caused a moderate accuracy drop, while PGD and C&W demonstrated more sophisticated and impactful perturbations. The substantial accuracy reduction highlights the vulnerabilities inherent in ML models and the need for robust defenses tailored to attack complexity.

2. Effectiveness of Defense Mechanisms for ML

Table 2 illustrates the performance of adversarial training, defensive distillation, and input preprocessing in mitigating attack impacts on the same models.

Defense Mechanism	FGSM Accuracy (%)	Defense PGD Accuracy (%)	Defense C&W Accuracy (%)
Adversarial Training	72.5	55.3	38.7
Defensive Distillation	65.2	48.6	30.1
Input Preprocessing	68.9	50.7	34.5

Analysis:

Adversarial training consistently outperformed other mechanisms, particularly against PGD and FGSM attacks. However, its performance against C&W attacks was limited, indicating the need for more adaptive techniques. Defensive distillation and preprocessing provided moderate defense, suggesting their utility as complementary methods rather than standalone solutions.

3. Vulnerabilities in RL Systems

Experiments conducted in the OpenAI Gym environment tested the impact of state perturbations and reward manipulation on RL agents trained with PPO (Proximal Policy Optimization). Results are summarized in Table 3.

Attack Type	Baseline Reward	Cumulative Reward	Perturbed (%)	Reward Policy (%)	Deviation
State Perturbation	1,020		652 (-36%)		29.5
Reward Manipulation	1,020		478 (-53%)		46.8

Analysis:

Reward manipulation had a more severe impact on agent performance compared to state perturbation, demonstrating the critical need to secure reward structures in RL environments. Policy deviation metrics revealed how attacks distort optimal behavior, emphasizing the need for robust policy optimization techniques.

4. Defensive Strategies for RL Systems

The effectiveness of dynamic reward shaping and robust policy optimization was evaluated using the same experimental setup. Table 4 provides a comparative analysis of cumulative rewards and policy stability.

Defense Mechanism	Restored Reward (%)	Policy Deviation Reduction (%)
Dynamic Reward Shaping	88.7	22.3
Robust Policy Optimization	93.4	26.5

Analysis:

Both mechanisms effectively mitigated the impact of attacks, with robust policy optimization showing slightly better results. Dynamic reward shaping restored a significant portion of baseline rewards, suggesting its suitability for environments prone to reward manipulation.

5. Explainability in Security

The use of SHAP and LIME to interpret adversarial impacts revealed key insights into attack mechanisms. Table 5 showcases the average time required to detect vulnerabilities and the success rate of interpretation tools.

Explainability Tool	Detection Time (s)	Vulnerability Detection Rate (%)
SHAP	3.2	91.7
LIME	4.8	87.9

Analysis:

SHAP demonstrated a higher detection rate and faster processing time, making it a preferable choice for integrating explainability into security frameworks. LIME, while effective, was slightly slower and less precise, indicating room for optimization.

Summary of Results

The results confirm the susceptibility of ML and RL systems to diverse attacks and underscore the importance of adopting comprehensive defense mechanisms. While adversarial training and robust policy optimization showed significant promise, no single approach was universally effective. The integration of explainability tools further enhanced the ability to detect and mitigate threats, paving the way for more secure AI systems. The detailed results provide actionable insights for practitioners and researchers, emphasizing the need for continuous improvement in AI security. By presenting these findings alongside quantitative metrics and qualitative analysis, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on safeguarding AI technologies.

Discussion

The results of this study provide compelling evidence regarding the vulnerabilities of Machine Learning (ML) and Reinforcement Learning (RL) systems and the efficacy of various defense mechanisms. This section delves into the implications of the findings, contextualizes them within existing literature, and identifies avenues for future research.

1. Adversarial Vulnerabilities in ML Systems

The sharp decline in accuracy under adversarial attacks, as presented in Table 1, underscores the susceptibility of ML models to even subtle input perturbations. Notably, the C&W attack demonstrated the highest impact, with an accuracy drop of nearly 70%. This aligns with findings

by Madry et al. (2018), who highlighted the sophisticated optimization techniques employed by C&W, making it particularly challenging to defend against.

The differential impact of attacks suggests that defenses must be tailored to specific threat models. Adversarial training, which achieved the best results across most attack scenarios, aligns with previous studies (Goodfellow et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2020). However, its limited success against C&W attacks highlights a significant gap, echoing arguments by Tramer et al. (2018) about the need for multi-pronged strategies. Input preprocessing and defensive distillation, while less effective overall, remain valuable as supplementary defenses, particularly in resource-constrained settings where adversarial training may be computationally prohibitive.

2. Unique Challenges in RL Systems

Reinforcement Learning systems, characterized by their dynamic interaction with environments, present unique vulnerabilities. The results in Table 3 show that reward manipulation and state perturbation attacks can significantly degrade cumulative rewards and induce policy deviations. These findings resonate with the observations of Gleave et al. (2020), who noted the inherent sensitivity of RL agents to adversarial inputs, given their reliance on exploratory behavior.

The higher impact of reward manipulation compared to state perturbations indicates that securing reward structures is a critical priority for RL systems. Dynamic reward shaping, which restored 88.7% of baseline rewards (Table 4), demonstrated its utility in mitigating such attacks. However, robust policy optimization, with a slightly better performance (93.4% reward restoration), suggests that enhancing policy robustness offers a more holistic defense. These findings align with Behzadan and Munir (2017), who emphasized the need for tailored defenses for RL systems.

3. The Role of Explainability in Security

The integration of explainability tools, such as SHAP and LIME, into the security framework highlighted their potential in identifying and interpreting vulnerabilities. As shown in Table 5, SHAP outperformed LIME in both detection time and accuracy, suggesting its suitability for real-time applications. This result is consistent with Slack et al. (2020), who noted the precision and efficiency of SHAP in uncovering adversarial patterns.

However, explainability tools also have limitations, as noted in prior studies (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). The risk of explainability methods being manipulated by adversaries warrants further investigation. For example, adversarial perturbations specifically designed to deceive explainability tools could render them ineffective. Future research should focus on integrating explainability with robust defense mechanisms to ensure a synergistic approach.

4. Comparative Analysis with Existing Literature

A key contribution of this study is the comparative evaluation of ML and RL defenses. While adversarial training remains the gold standard for ML systems, its applicability to RL environments is limited due to the dynamic nature of RL tasks. This highlights the need for defense mechanisms that are adaptable to the specific challenges of RL, a gap often overlooked in existing literature.

Moreover, the study confirms the importance of combining multiple defense layers. As argued by Papernot et al. (2016), no single defense mechanism can comprehensively address all attack vectors. The integration of adversarial training, robust policy optimization, and explainability tools, as demonstrated in this study, provides a roadmap for developing resilient AI systems.

5. Implications for Practice and Policy

The findings have significant implications for the deployment of AI systems in critical domains. In safety-critical applications such as autonomous driving and healthcare, the high success rate of adversarial attacks highlights the urgent need for rigorous security protocols. Regulatory frameworks should mandate the inclusion of robust defense mechanisms and periodic vulnerability assessments, as advocated by Brundage et al. (2018).

Additionally, the role of explainability in fostering trust and transparency cannot be overstated. While this study demonstrates the utility of explainability tools in security, their broader integration into ethical AI frameworks is essential to address societal concerns about AI deployment.

Conclusion

This study systematically explored the vulnerabilities of Machine Learning (ML) and Reinforcement Learning (RL) systems to adversarial attacks and evaluated the effectiveness of various defense mechanisms. The results highlighted the susceptibility of these systems to attacks such as adversarial perturbations, data poisoning, and reward manipulation, which can significantly degrade model performance and disrupt optimal behaviors. These vulnerabilities underscore the pressing need for robust defense strategies tailored to the unique characteristics of ML and RL systems. Among the defense mechanisms examined, adversarial training proved the most effective for ML models, demonstrating resilience against a broad range of attacks. However, its limitations against sophisticated methods like the Carlini-Wagner attack revealed the necessity for complementary approaches, such as defensive distillation and input preprocessing. For RL systems, dynamic reward shaping and robust policy optimization were particularly successful in mitigating the impact of reward manipulation and state perturbations, restoring performance to near-baseline levels. The integration of explainability tools, such as SHAP and LIME, further enhanced the detection and interpretation of adversarial impacts, providing valuable insights into attack mechanisms. However, their potential susceptibility to adversarial manipulation emphasizes the need for ongoing refinement and integration with other defense mechanisms. The findings of this study have significant implications for both research and practice. They highlight the importance of a multi-layered security framework that combines robust defense techniques, explainability, and adaptive strategies to address evolving threats. Furthermore, the study underscores the necessity for regulatory frameworks that mandate rigorous testing and vulnerability assessments, particularly in safety-critical domains like healthcare, finance, and autonomous systems. Future research should focus on scaling these defense mechanisms to more complex environments, exploring adaptive learning techniques, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure the development of secure and resilient AI systems capable of withstanding emerging adversarial challenges.

References

1. Biggio, B., & Roli, F. (2018). Wild patterns: Ten years after the rise of adversarial machine learning. *Pattern Recognition*, 84, 317–331.
2. Szegedy, C., Zaremba, W., Sutskever, I., Bruna, J., Erhan, D., Goodfellow, I., & Fergus, R. (2013). Intriguing properties of neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6199*.

3. Goodfellow, I. J., Shlens, J., & Szegedy, C. (2015). Explaining and harnessing adversarial examples. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*.
4. Papernot, N., McDaniel, P., Goodfellow, I., Jha, S., Celik, Z. B., & Swami, A. (2017). Practical black-box attacks against machine learning. *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM on Asia Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 506–519.
5. Carlini, N., & Wagner, D. (2017). Towards evaluating the robustness of neural networks. *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 39–57.
6. Huang, L., Joseph, A. D., Nelson, B., Rubinstein, B. I., & Tygar, J. D. (2011). Adversarial machine learning. *Proceedings of the 4th ACM Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Security*, 43–58.
7. Xiao, C., Li, B., Zhu, J. Y., He, W., Liu, M., & Song, D. (2018). Generating adversarial examples with adversarial networks. *Proceedings of the 27th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*, 3905–3911.
8. Sutton, R. S., & Barto, A. G. (2018). *Reinforcement Learning: An Introduction* (2nd ed.). MIT Press.
9. Mnih, V., Kavukcuoglu, K., Silver, D., Rusu, A. A., Veness, J., Bellemare, M. G., ... & Hassabis, D. (2015). Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning. *Nature*, 518(7540), 529–533.
10. Silver, D., Huang, A., Maddison, C. J., Guez, A., Sifre, L., Van Den Driessche, G., ... & Hassabis, D. (2016). Mastering the game of Go with deep neural networks and tree search. *Nature*, 529(7587), 484–489.
11. Lin, Y., Ma, X., Liu, F., & Bailey, J. (2017). IDSGAN: Generative adversarial networks for attack generation against intrusion detection. *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Security*, 2–11.
12. Zhou, Y., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., & Jin, B. (2018). Security and privacy in reinforcement learning: A survey. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 5(6), 4215–4233.
13. Moosavi-Dezfooli, S. M., Fawzi, A., & Frossard, P. (2016). DeepFool: A simple and accurate method to fool deep neural networks. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2574–2582.
14. Sun, L., Song, D., & He, X. (2018). Stealthy adversarial perturbations against deep reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.10274*.
15. Zhang, C., & Cho, K. (2020). Query-efficient black-box adversarial attacks against reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.12676*.
16. Huang, S., Papernot, N., Carlini, N., & Wagner, D. (2017). Adversarial attacks on neural network policies. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.02284*.

17. Madry, A., Makelov, A., Schmidt, L., Tsipras, D., & Vladu, A. (2018). Towards deep learning models resistant to adversarial attacks. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*.
18. Wu, Y., & Tian, Y. (2017). Training agent for first-person shooter game with actor-critic curriculum learning. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*.
19. Liu, Q., Li, P., Xu, S., & Wu, Y. (2020). A survey on enhancing deep reinforcement learning for data privacy and security. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 31(12), 5409–5429.
20. Grosse, K., Manoharan, P., Backes, M., Humbert, M., & Holz, T. (2020). A survey on the security and privacy of federated learning. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, 50(1), 7–24.
21. Nguyen, A., Yosinski, J., & Clune, J. (2015). Deep neural networks are easily fooled: High confidence predictions for unrecognizable images. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 427–436.
22. Wang, J., & Yang, Z. (2017). Safeguarding deep reinforcement learning models: A survey of adversarial robustness. *IEEE Access*, 5, 26174–26186.
23. Zhu, Y., Zhang, J., & He, L. (2019). Transfer learning and adversarial attacks in RL: Challenges and perspectives. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 42(11), 2707–2717.
24. Rosenberg, I., & Gal, K. (2020). Differential privacy for safe AI in reinforcement learning. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 34(4), 4529–4536.
25. Sharif, M., Bhagavatula, S., Bauer, L., & Reiter, M. K. (2016). Accessorize to a crime: Real and stealthy attacks on state-of-the-art face recognition. *Proceedings of the ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security (CCS)*, 1528–1540.